

18TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CHEMISTRY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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Venue:

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CA' FOSCARI UNIVERSITY OF VENICE (ITALY)

Book of Abstracts

Ca' Foscari
University
of Venice

EuChemS
European Chemical Society

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Executive Board of the European Chemical Society, I wish you a warm welcome to this 18th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment. The European Chemical Society – in short EuChemS – is an overarching society at the European level with over 50 national member societies as members. In this way, EuChemS represents approximately 130,000 chemists from all over Europe. Did you ever realize that by being a member of your national society, you are a member of EuChemS too?

The slogan of this conference is 'Towards a pollution free society', which is well aligned with activities from EuChemS. The European Commission recently set up the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform and EuChemS was invited to join. The platform will effectively mainstream the zero pollution agenda by bringing together stakeholders and experts of different policy areas, including health, agriculture, research and innovation, transport, digitalization and the environment. EuChemS will emphasize to address the Zero Pollution challenges from the chemistry perspective in a science-based approach.

I am here in the Netherlands, but you are in the beautiful city of Venice, that I am sure will inspire you to have fruitful and constructive discussions on how to get to zero pollution and how to address many other challenges to create a sustainable environment. I wish you a very enjoyable conference!

Floris Rutjens

President of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS)

Exposure to Mercury as Environmental Pollutant Among Lung Adenocarcinoma Patients in Vojvodina

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The exponential increase of industrial, agricultural and technological development lead to continuous chronic environmental and occupational exposure to mercury (Hg). The association between mercury and lung cancer is not completely understood, although Hg exposure has been correlated with skin, prostate and renal cancer. In this study, 36 male patients (39-84 y) with IIIB and IV stage inoperable lung adenocarcinoma from the Institute for Lung disease of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica were enrolled. The mercury content was determined by ICP-MS in their morning urine samples. None of the patients was professional exposed to Hg. Mercury was detected in 91.67% (33/36) urine samples among which only one had value below the median urinary value (0.140 µg/L) for healthy adults given by the Tox Guide of the US Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. Furthermore, 63.89% (23/36) lung cancer patients exceeded the 95th percentile urinary Hg value (1.8 µg/L) for US. Taking in account the reference value when no adverse effects could be expected, 47.22% (17/36) of the observed patients surpassed 5 µg Hg/gCr or 27.78% (10/36) exceeded 7 µg Hg/L urinary level. There were no statistical differences in Hg urinary levels between patients with amalgam dental fillings (7.310±13.184 µg Hg/gCr) in comparison to those without (8.405±11.594 µg Hg/gCr). Almost 50% of lung adenocarcinoma patients (with inoperable IIIB-IV stage) from Vojvodina are exposed to mercury above levels when no adverse effects could be expected. Environmental pollution should be presumed as the main source of exposure to mercury.

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